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Teachers as Creative Agents:

How Self-Beliefs and Self-Regulation Drive Teachers' Creative Activity

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Abstract

Across two studies, we explore how teachers' creative self-beliefs and self-regulation drive their creativity when faced with complex projects. In Study 1, 173 teachers reported on the most creative project they carried out last year and provided data on their creative self-beliefs (confidence and centrality of creativity) and self-regulation when pursuing projects. Creative self-beliefs were positively associated with the likelihood of obtaining more creative outcomes, both directly and indirectly, by strengthening teachers' self-regulation. Moreover, highly innovative projects were unlikely if teachers' beliefs and self-regulation were low. A latent profile analysis demonstrated three different approaches to carrying out and managing creative projects, resulting in varying levels of creativity in the final projects. These findings were extended and elaborated in a mixed-method Study 2, involving 16 teachers who participated in an intensive 10-week, microlongitudinal diary study and in-depth interviews. This study demonstrated that creative self-regulation allowed the teachers to plan and monitor their actions more effectively, resulting in more creative products. We discuss the role of self-beliefs and self-regulation in teachers' creative agency and recommend future studies and practical interventions.

Keywords: self-regulation; teachers' creativity; mix-method; creative agency

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Contrary to widely-advertised claims (see, e.g., Robinson, 2007) and shared beliefs (Benedek et al., 2021), education plays a crucial and mostly positive role in developing students' creative thinking (Gajda, Karwowski, et al., 2017) and strengthening their agency. Creativity—understood as an activity that leads to original and relevant outcomes (Runco & Jaeger, 2012)—requires knowledge and intellectual skills (e.g., intelligence, Karwowski et al., 2021; or divergent thinking, Said-Metwaly et al., 2022), but also self-regulation (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017). Creative tasks are often cloudy and vague, so there is no “one size fits all” recipe for creativity: open problems require various approaches. These approaches often rely on divergence: searching for multiple ideas and exploring different directions. Yet, creating something also requires convergence: deciding where to go and what solution to choose. In short, creative action is balanced action—effectively bridging divergence and convergence, spontaneity and control.

This paper is built on the premise that the existing scholarly understanding of teachers' creativity is insufficient. The literature provides dozens of studies exploring what teachers think about students' creativity (Mullet et al., 2016), whether they can recognize creative students (Gralewski & Karwowski, 2018), what ways of developing creativity they declare (Rubenstein, Ridgley, et al., 2018), and actually use in their classrooms (Gajda, Beghetto, et al., 2017). Yet what do we know about how teachers create, especially concerning creativity in a school-related context? The short answer is: “not much.”

Therefore, in this paper, we seek to fill this gap. Across two studies, we explore teachers' self-regulation during projects that require creative thinking. In Study 1, we examine the role of creative self-beliefs (creative confidence, or the “I can” type conviction, and the centrality of creativity, or the “I am” type conviction) and self-regulation for obtaining more-versus-less creative effects. Study 2 applies mixed-method dynamic approaches (a microlongitudinal quantitative diary

study supplemented by qualitative in-depth interviews) to understand teachers' creativity in an ecologically-valid context: a competition for teachers, who—together with their students—worked over nearly three months to develop original and useful educational aids. How did they approach the problem and regulate their activity? What did this process look like? These are the central questions of Study 2.

In what follows, we unpack the theoretical categories explored in our studies. Then, we overview the two studies in more detail alongside their main findings. Finally, we discuss the consequences of our project for teachers' creative functioning.

Situating Teachers' Creativity

Apart from well-accepted understandings of creativity in the literature, i.e., perceiving it as leading to original and useful outcomes (Runco & Jaeger, 2012; Sternberg & Lubart, 1998), there are debates over the most appropriate definition of creativity (Kharkhurin, 2014; Simonton, 2012) and its various classifications and hierarchies (Glăveanu & Beghetto, 2021; Kaufman & Beghetto, 2009). This complexity becomes even more pervasive when creativity is analyzed in educational settings. What seems to be widely accepted is that creativity requires both originality and relevance. Ideas, behaviors, and original but useless products are not creative, just as those appropriate and relevant ones, but lacking originality. Yet, how do those general categories apply to teachers' creativity?

In an influential review, Plucker et al. (2004, p. 90) defined creativity as "the interaction among aptitude, process, and environment by which an individual or group produces a perceptible product that is both novel and useful as defined within a social context." This definition successfully integrates classic attempts that focus on one of the four aspects of creativity, i.e., person, product, process, or press (Rhodes, 1961) and emphasizes the interaction of these factors in what makes creativity possible. This is precisely why recent theories of creativity make an effort to dynamize it and propose to analyze creativity as an inter-individual "action" (instead of the intraindividual process) of various "actors" (rather than persons), who generate "artifacts" (rather than products) in

the face of “audience” (rather than being influenced by the press), utilizing “affordances” and constraints created by the domain and the activity itself (Glăveanu, 2013).

Thus, creativity in the classroom—both the creativity of teachers and their students—is dynamic and interactive (Gajda, Beghetto, et al., 2017; Kupers et al., 2019). It is not limited to mental processes like divergent thinking (de Chantal et al., 2020). Yet, it also rarely ends up at the level of outstanding achievements that are socially recognized and acclaimed. Using the categories of the most broadly accepted creativity theory (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2009), teachers’ and students’ creativity starts with the mini-c level, i.e., the level of mental processes and operations relevant to creative thought. It involves divergent thinking, making remote associations, using analogies (Beaty & Kenett, 2023; Denervaud et al., 2021), and reasoning (Dumas, 2018) to solve problems. This mini-c creativity level is critical for learning processes (Beghetto, 2016a; Karwowski et al., 2020) and serves as a building block for the next levels of creativity. But this is rather the next level—little-c creativity—mostly analyzed when classroom creativity is considered. Little-c creativity involves problem-solving and developing new products without expecting them to result in revolutionary discoveries and achievements. Operating at the personal and micro-interpersonal (classroom, peer group) level, this form of creativity can be valuable individually and useful in interpersonal teaching and learning contexts. Thus, a teacher who develops an original and appropriate way of explaining fractions or creates an ad hoc aid to help their students better understand the subject matter demonstrates little-c creativity. At the same time, however, teachers might (and often do) show Pro-c creativity, where “Pro” stands for “professional.” This form of creativity results in novel and useful solutions in professional work, starting from organizing the learning process using self-developed methods and aids to new artifacts. Big-C creativity, the fourth level in Kaufman and Beghetto’s (2009) model, characterizes the most outstanding figures in the field and genius-level accomplishments, thus being outside our interest here.

Consequently, teachers’ creativity might be understood as a particular form of action in the face of students and colleagues. This action might lead to new and original artifacts, making teaching

and learning more effective. However, the action itself, even without any artifact, may hold a certain level of novelty and value, as visible in “creative teaching” (Beghetto, 2017). What is poorly understood is how this creative action happens. What makes teachers willing to engage in creative activities and conduct them successfully? One key element could be the teachers’ sense of agency and the ability to self-regulate while solving complex and ill-defined problems: the factors we focus on below.

On Exerting Creative Agency

People’s agency stems from their belief systems (Bandura, 2001). What people think about creativity, including their own, influences whether they will function creatively in real life (Karwowski & Kaufman, 2017). This reasoning is well-established in the educational psychology literature, such as in work demonstrating the importance of self-beliefs (e.g., academic self-concept or self-efficacy) for students’ academic achievement or well-being (e.g., Lazowski & Hulleman, 2016; Yeager et al., 2019) as well as teachers’ outcomes (Perera & John, 2020). Beliefs about creativity play a similar role in creative expression: they might hinder or facilitate creative activity. Put differently, they intervene in the relationship between creative potential (i.e., abilities and skills) and behavior, as posited by the Creative Behavior as Agentic Action Model (CBAA; Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). Thus, creativity-related self-beliefs (“creative self-beliefs”; Karwowski, Lebuda, et al., 2019) affect how people exercise their creative agency.

Two types of self-beliefs through which creative agency operates have been intensively studied in the last two decades. The first is *creative confidence*, which reflects a person’s trust in their creative competencies. Conceptually, creative confidence might represent a relatively stable trait or a more dynamic, task-specific state. When creative confidence is analyzed in a trait-like manner, it denotes people’s generalized self-perception about their creativity: creative self-concept. Measures of creative self-concept are similar to the well-known instruments for measuring academic self-concept (Marsh et al., 2005), the only difference being that they refer to creativity rather than academic subjects. On the other hand, when creative confidence is operationalized as a more

dynamic, task- and situation-specific phenomenon, it resembles creative self-efficacy, i.e., more changeable and malleable self-perception. In this article, particularly Study 1, we focus on the role played by relatively stable aspects of creative confidence as possible drivers of teachers' creative behaviors, although we do see merit in the postulates present in the literature to conceptualize (creative) self-efficacy as a dynamic and task-related characteristic (Karwowski et al., 2019; Marsh et al., 2019).

Creative centrality, in turn, describes how vital creativity is for people's self-perception and identity. Various alternative labels have been applied to denote creative centrality, the two most often used being "creative personal identity" (Karwowski et al., 2018) and "creative role identity" (Huang et al., 2019). Both refer to the place creativity occupies in an individual's personal or work identity. Is it important to me to be a creative teacher? Is being creative central to my self-perception as a person? Those are the questions creative centrality focuses on.

Previous work has shown that creative confidence and centrality explain a unique portion of the variance in people's creative successes and activities (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). These two constructs are often modeled as a higher-order factor (Lebuda et al., 2021; Zielińska et al., 2022b). Those models show that although achieving creative outcomes depends on various variables and a positive conviction about one's creativity does not guarantee success, holding creative self-beliefs might be necessary for successfully tackling creative challenges.

Following this logic, we posit that teachers are no exception here, and there are reasons to believe that their creative self-beliefs affect whether they introduce creativity to educational practice. Of course, creative self-beliefs are not the only factor driving or constraining teachers' creative agency. Their readiness to act creatively must not be isolated from environmental influences, including schools' cultural and structural characteristics (Deschênes & Parent, 2022). Yet, focusing on teachers' self-beliefs brings at least three important implications.

First, how teachers perceive creativity, including their creative ability and its value in day-to-day functioning, makes them less or more inclined to teach creatively: to apply original and effective

teaching strategies (Lasky & Yoon, 2011; Sak, 2004). Along with the often-reported challenges related to educational systems, such as rigid curricula or the prevalence of high-stakes standardized tests (e.g., Aljughaiman & Mowrer-Reynolds, 2005), teachers' negative self-beliefs might offer an explanation for why they generally feel unprepared to put creativity into their pedagogical practice (Patston et al., 2018). Given social modeling, through which students might feel encouraged to take action just from observing a teacher who does so (Bandura, 1997; Jeffrey & Craft, 2004), stimulating teachers' readiness to teach creatively becomes even more essential (Beghetto, 2017). Yet, to do this effectively, it seems necessary first to address teachers' creative self-beliefs.

A second consequence is more indirect and touches on how teachers' self-beliefs affect students' educational experiences (ten Hagen et al., 2022). Teachers' beliefs are reflected in their attitudes and behavior toward students. Teachers who see themselves as creative consider student characteristics conducive to creativity (e.g., independence or readiness to take risks) more desirable in the classroom (Kettler et al., 2018). Those who are not confident often discard students' creative ideas (Beghetto, 2009). Some inaccurate beliefs about creativity also impair teachers' ability to recognize the creative potential of their students (e.g., Gralewski & Karwowski, 2018) and, presumably, shape their expectations for their students' learning (Rubie-Davies et al., 2012). Therefore, teachers' creative self-beliefs might facilitate or hinder students' development.

The third consequence relates to the indirect role of creative self-beliefs via self-regulation and the importance of self-regulation for achieving creative outcomes. Self-regulation includes goal-setting, formulating an action plan, self-observation, and self-reflection (Bandura, 1991, 1997). Students' academic self-efficacy predicts their academic performance directly and via self-regulatory efforts (e.g., Jung et al., 2017; Koh et al., 2022). At the same time, however, most studies examined the *self-beliefs – self-regulation – performance* link by focusing on separate portions of this chain rather than by taking a more complex approach that considers all these elements (see, e.g., Honicke & Broadbent, 2016, for an overview).

Similarly, while the link between creative self-beliefs and creative performance is well-established (e.g., Haase et al., 2018), much less is known about the mechanism underlying this relationship (but see, e.g., Intasao & Hao, 2018; Redifer et al., 2021; Zielińska, Lebuda, & Karwowski, 2022a). Do people who believe in their creative abilities act differently and perform better, and if so, how does it happen? Based on theoretical models (Bandura, 1997; Karwowski et al., 2022; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2021), we propose that creative self-beliefs make people more efficient in regulating their behavior. Consider someone with high creative confidence and centrality. They are expected to purposefully and efficiently increase their efforts, persevere in the face of hurdles, cope better with the emotional demands of the challenge, observe progress, and pursue their set goal strategically. Given that a person's sense of efficacy is often built upon previous successful attempts (i.e., mastery experience, Bandura, 1997), it is also plausible that more confident individuals will apply various heuristics (e.g., self-regulatory tactics) that have worked in the past. However, studies examining how people self-regulate, i.e., execute, attune, and motivate their actions during the creative process, are scarce. Below, we briefly overview the recent attempts to describe the nature of creative self-regulation.

Self-regulation for Creative Action

Teachers often encounter ill-defined problems that cannot be solved with routine formulas; consider, for example, the transition to distance and remote learning caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Finding ways of approaching such challenges does not come down to just having an idea; equally demanding is turning such an idea into action (Boldt, 2019). This requires motivational strengths, allowing one to persevere, and cognitive and metacognitive tools that enable one to do the actual work. In short, it requires effective self-regulation.

Self-regulation depends on various cognitive (e.g., planning), metacognitive (e.g., monitoring), affective (e.g., managing emotions), and motivational (e.g., goal orientation) factors. Of several existing theoretical frameworks of self-regulation (see, e.g., Panadero, 2017, for a review), one model (Zimmerman, 2000) has been recently applied to capture the control mechanisms

embedded in the creative process (Rubenstein, Callan, et al., 2018; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2021). It has been observed that people who self-regulate their creative activity—both short-term laboratory tasks (Callan et al., 2019, 2021) and longer-term projects (Zielińska et al., 2022, 2023)—go through similar phases as when engaging in learning. In the preparatory phase, they plan their work and set goals: motivational beliefs such as self-efficacy or expectations about the forthcoming activity fuel this preparation and the outcome. Moving on to the second phase, performance, includes employing cognitive strategies to handle a task, monitoring the effectiveness of these strategies, and regulating their usage. The self-regulatory cycle ends with self-reflection, allowing one to evaluate the results and working methods. This is accompanied by emotional reactions reflecting one's assessment of the outcome. Each phase influences the subsequent step; thus, the self-regulation process is cyclical.

What distinguishes creative pursuits from other goal-directed activities is the pervasive experience of uncertainty (Beghetto, 2021). When engaging in a creative activity, neither the goal nor the steps toward its attainment are precisely specified. This requires adaptability resources to navigate the action effectively (Martin et al., 2012). Therefore, self-regulation for creative action employs two sets of mechanisms: revising and re-strategizing, and sustaining and maintaining (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017).

A recent study (Zielińska et al., 2022) applied a three-phase cyclical model to explore the self-regulatory mechanisms adolescents use while pursuing creative projects. Young people guided their creative activity using different mechanisms before starting the project, during its performance, and after completing the work. The preparation phase included expectations regarding the process, namely uncertainty acceptance and anticipating obstacles. In the performance phase, adolescents navigated activity by adjusting their approach, managing and reframing goals, regulating emotions, and dealing with obstacles. Finally, they reflected on the whole process by improving their approach and building readiness to share the outcomes with others. Overall, adolescents in this study who used a richer repertoire of various self-regulatory mechanisms achieved more creative results as assessed by independent experts.

Understanding how students guide their actions to achieve creative goals is instrumental in teaching creativity. Teachers' self-regulation is essential for precisely the same reasons. As the sociocognitive perspective on self-regulation (Bandura, 1997) explains, teachers may promote self-regulated learning both directly and indirectly (i.e., by creating a supportive environment, Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014; Davies et al., 2013). Thus, as long as explicit training and favorable conditions are provided, students also learn to self-regulate by observing their teachers (Dignath & Veenman, 2021; Groenendijk, 2013; Paris & Paris, 2001). For this reason, it is crucial to understand how teachers approach creative tasks and activities and what role their creative self-beliefs and self-regulation play in this process. This is the main research problem of the two studies presented below.

The Present Studies

The two studies we report herein examined the role of teachers' creative self-beliefs and self-regulation in pursuing creative projects. The conceptual assertions tested across both studies are depicted in Figure 1. In Study 1, a group of teachers responded to a scale measuring their creative self-beliefs, described the most creative projects they had completed within the last year, and provided retrospectively framed creative self-regulation items. Additionally, the projects were assessed for creativity by judges. Study 1 was built on three hypotheses. The first (H1) posited that more effective self-regulation would be associated with higher project creativity. The second (H2) considered teachers' creative self-beliefs as a factor that makes creative self-regulation more likely. More specifically, we hypothesized that creative self-beliefs would be associated with the creativity of teachers' projects both directly and indirectly (via creative self-regulation). Our third hypothesis (H3) expected creative self-beliefs and self-regulation to be necessary conditions for the final project's level of creativity. In other words, we hypothesized that creative self-beliefs are necessary for creative self-regulation (H3a) and that low creative self-beliefs and poor creative self-regulation would make achieving a highly creative project unlikely (H3b). While our analyses primarily utilized variable-centered analytical approaches, we exploratorily applied a person-centered analytical solution. Using latent profile analysis, we sought to identify diverse configurations of creative self-

regulation factors among teachers and examine how those different profiles relate to teachers' creative self-beliefs and the results of their projects.

Study 2 utilized a mixed-method intensive design. We took advantage of a real-life creative situation: the "Science for You" competition organized by the Copernicus Science Center in Warsaw, Poland (see <https://www.kopernik.org.pl/en>). Teachers (individually or in dyads) and teams formed by their students (4-5 students in each team) developed an educational aid. We were interested in how teachers' self-regulation would change throughout working on the project and be associated with their perception of the final product's creativity. In the qualitative part of Study 2, we delved into the nuances of teachers' self-regulation, acknowledging the collaborative efforts the project entailed. We explored teachers' specific regulatory approaches across different project stages, looking for insights into students' roles in this process.

Figure 1
The Conceptual Model Tested Across Study 1 and Study 2

Study 1

Method

Participants

A convenience sample of one hundred seventy-three teachers (147 females) participated in Study 1. They were recruited through teacher online communities as well as directly approached by research assistants in several schools across Poland. All participants who identified as teachers and provided a sufficiently detailed description of the undertaken creative project were included in the analyses. Teachers' age ranged from 23 to 68 years ($M = 44.40$; $SD = 9.17$). Most participants were experienced teachers—their experience ranged from 4 months to 47 years in the profession, with an average of 18.31 years ($SD = 10.69$). Teachers predominantly (91%) taught in primary schools.

Measures

Creative Self-Beliefs. We used a modified Short Scale of Creative Self (SSCS; Karwowski et al., 2018; Zielińska, Lebuda, & Karwowski, 2022b) to measure two aspects of teachers' creative self-beliefs: creative confidence (seven items, e.g.: "I'm good at proposing original solutions of my students' problems," McDonald's $\omega = .93$) and the centrality of creativity (four items, e.g.: "I consider myself a creative teacher," $\omega = .83$). Two modifications were made to the scale. First, we modified some items to denote opinions associated with teachers' work instead of the general self-description of the original SSCS (see Supplementary Online Material [SOM] Table S1 for the original and modified SSCS). Second, teachers provided their responses using a 9-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *definitely not* to 9 = *definitely yes*. This modified scale was piloted on an independent sample of 287 teachers and demonstrated a good fit to the theoretically expected hierarchical creative agency model, composed of two lower-order factors of confidence and centrality ($CFI = .995$, $TLI = .994$). Therefore, we used the general creative self-beliefs score in this study, averaged across all 11 items ($\omega = .95$).

Creative Projects. Following the procedure outlined by Zielińska and colleagues (2022), teachers were asked an open-ended question about their most creative educational project performed last year. The instruction was: "We often do creative things: we write, paint, invent

something. But creativity is not just about the arts: it can also relate to coming up with an original gift for a friend, designing clothes or jewelry, solving a technical problem, or finding a new and meaningful way to spend your free time. Think for a moment about your most creative activity in the past year in the education domain, i.e., about an action that required ingenuity and a fresh perspective and yielded an effect you were satisfied with. Briefly describe this activity below.”

Teachers’ projects were rated for creativity through the Consensual Assessment Technique (CAT; Amabile, 1982). This scoring method assumes that the best measure of any product’s creativity is the combined assessment of independent judges, ideally experts in a field. Thus, instead of specifying the explicit criteria to deem a product creative, the scores are based on the judges’ implicit, personal meanings of creativity, and their consensus serves as the evaluation foundation. The CAT has proved effective, i.e., valid and reliable, in various contexts and across products assessed, including verbal divergent thinking tasks (Silvia et al., 2008), musical compositions (Hickey, 2001), drawings (Dollinger & Shafran, 2005), and teaching designs (Cheng, 2018; but see Anderson et al., 2023 for a critical discussion on the CAT’s applications). In this study, three judges (the first, second, and last authors of this article, experienced in assessing various creative artifacts) independently scored the creativity of the presented projects. Specifically, given the longer-term, project-like character of teachers’ creative initiatives than we target in this study—rather than ad hoc creative acts—the judges scored the projects for both originality (using a scale from 1 = *not original* to 5 = *very original*; $\alpha = .90$) and complexity (using a scale from 1 = *noncomplex* to 5 = *very complex*; $\alpha = .86$). These scores were highly interrelated at the judge level (judge 1: $\alpha = .86$, judge 2: $\alpha = .86$, judge 3: $\alpha = .91$), so we calculated a composite creativity score for each judge as an average of their originality and complexity ratings. The judges’ creativity scores were reliable ($\alpha = .91$, $ICC_{3,k} = .91$, 95% CI [.89, .93]), so the ratings were averaged to yield each teacher’s final creativity score. Examples of projects scored as less or more creative are provided in Table 1.

Table 1

Examples of More and Less Creative Projects as Assessed by the Judges

Creativity Score	Project Description
Low Project Creativity	
1.67	Solving a technical problem at work.
1.67	Actions based on stimulating children's internal motivation. Not using rewards and punishments as external motivation.
1.67	Point-based grading system.
1.83	Practical exercises during classes.
2.33	In the past year, I worked with students remotely. For this purpose, I searched for ways and methods to convey as much information to the students as possible. I connected with them via the internet. Given that I'm not of the younger generation and computers have never been my strong suit, this posed a significant challenge for me. However, with the help of my colleagues and my own children, the problems were solved. As time went on, things got better.
High Project Creativity	
5.00	Work on an educational project related to coding and programming using robots and technological tools. In these classes, we used these tools to develop IT skills and competencies in a creative way, meaning that task ideas required creativity. The tasks were not based on ready-made ideas and available scenarios but on the teacher's and group's ideas during the classes. The final result was individual works such as an audiobook, a video recording on various topics, designing various things in graphic programs, or building models that were moved and programmed by students' robots.
5.00	Research project related to particulate pollution, the introduction of new technologies, working with microbits, and coming up with a research problem topic.
5.00	"Station: WEATHER"—together with students, we built a weather station using simple methods: a barometer, wind vane, anemometer, hygrometer, and rain gauge. Using these simple instruments, we investigated the weather.
5.00	"Optometry Project" is about examining eye relaxation using artificial intelligence to construct glasses for visually impaired people who read pedestrian crossings, creating eye relaxation exercises, building a 3D eye model, and developing manipulative boards for eye exercises.

Note. Creativity Score is the average of ratings from three judges.

Creative Self-Regulation. Teachers were provided retrospectively framed items related to their work on the project (Zielińska et al., 2022, 2023). Seven items referred to the forethought phase (i.e., before the work started) and covered two factors of creative self-regulation: obstacle expectations (two items, e.g.: "I knew that working on this project would not always be enjoyable," $\omega = .60$) and uncertainty acceptance (five items, e.g.: "I knew that I would not be able to predict all the steps to my project," $\omega = .70$). Thirteen items touched on the period of actually carrying out the activities required by the project, covering three factors: adjusting approach (five items, e.g.: "I was open to new opportunities when they came up during my project," $\omega = .84$), managing and reframing

goals (four items, e.g.: “While working on my project, I set more specific goals as time went on,” $\omega = .66$) and emotion regulation (four items, e.g.: “When things seemed difficult, I reminded myself that I was capable of doing it well,” $\omega = .78$). The last six items covered the self-reflection phase, measuring improving approach (three items, e.g.: “I was wondering if it could be done even better,” $\omega = .72$) and readiness for sharing (three items, e.g.: “I was happy to share the effects of my work with other people,” $\omega = .68$).

Procedure and Analytical Approach

Teachers were informed about the overall goals of Study 1 and provided informed consent to participate. Then, they were presented with the SSCS items, described their creative projects, and responded to self-regulation items.

Data analysis proceeded in six steps. We started with descriptive statistics and correlations between variables. Second, we conducted a hierarchical regression analysis, with the project’s creativity regressed on self-regulation factors. Given that the framing of the items explicitly covered pre-task (forethought), during the task (performance) and post-task (self-reflection) phases, we introduced predictors in three blocks. This allowed us to avoid problems associated with the multicollinearity of self-regulation factors identified elsewhere (Zielińska et al., 2023) and to estimate the unique proportion of variance associated with each phase, thus allowing us to test H1 more precisely.

Third, to test H2, we estimated a mediation model with creative self-beliefs as the predictor, creative self-regulation as a mediator, and the project’s creativity as a dependent variable. Given the sample size, we used an overall self-regulation factor in this model, obtained in second-order exploratory factor analysis (see SOM Table S2 for factor loadings).

Fourth, we conducted two Necessary Condition Analyses (NCA; Dul, 2016) to test H3a and H3b. Necessary logic proposes that a certain condition must be satisfied for a particular outcome to occur, e.g., high levels of a variable of interest. To test this reasoning, NCA examines a scatterplot that juxtaposes X variable, a potential necessary condition, against Y variable, a desired outcome.

Then, it identifies an empty space—the absence of data points—in the upper-left corner of the plot and draws a *ceiling line* to separate this area. The size of an empty corner illustrates the extent to which high levels of Y are unlikely with low X: a necessary-like pattern. This approach thus complements regression-based models by examining not only how the two variables co-occur but also whether one is indispensable for the other.

Our first NCA examined if creative self-beliefs are necessary for creative self-regulation. The second NCA considered both creative self-beliefs and creative self-regulation as necessary conditions for project creativity. We used ceiling regression-free disposal hull (CR-FDH d) as a measure of effect size, recommended by Dul (2016) for variables measured on interval or ratio scales, alongside the permutation-based significance test (Dul et al., 2020). The NCA effect size ranges from a theoretical minimum of 0 (indicating a lack of necessity) to a maximum of 1 and is calculated as the proportion of the empty space above the ceiling to the size of the entire area where observations can occur. Dul (2016) suggested the following criteria for assessing effect size: $0 < d < .10$ is considered a small effect, $.10 \leq d < .30$ represents a medium effect, $.30 \leq d < .50$ denotes a large effect, and $d \geq .50$ a very large effect (see Dul, 2016, for a discussion).

Fifth, we applied latent profile analysis (LPA; Collins & Lanza, 2009) to classify teachers employing different configurations of creative self-regulation factors. We determined the number of profiles to retain using several statistical criteria: entropy, the sample size-adjusted Bayesian information criterion (SABIC), the sample size-adjusted consistent Akaike information criterion (CAIC), and the bootstrapped likelihood test (BLRT). However, given the relatively low sample size for LPA (Nylund et al., 2007), we also aimed to choose a model that was as parsimonious as possible, thus facilitating interpretation and increasing the likelihood of replication in future research. Sixth and finally, we ran two between-subject analyses of variance (ANOVAs) to test for the differences in project creativity and creative self-beliefs across profiles of creative self-regulation.

The sensitivity analysis (G*Power 3.1.9.7, $\alpha = .05$, Power = .80) for multiple regression with seven self-regulation factors indicated that we could detect an effect size of $f^2 = .036$: a small-to-

medium effect, according to Cohen (Cohen, 1992; Lakens, 2013). We also hypothesized that the effect of teachers' creative self-beliefs on their creative performance might be mediated by creative self-regulation. Based on previous studies (Zielińska et al., 2022, 2023), we expected a relatively strong effect on the "a" path (creative self-beliefs – creative self-regulation, $\beta = .35$) and moderate effects on the "b" (creative self-regulation – creative performance) and "c" (creative self-beliefs – creative performance) paths; both $\beta = .22$: typical effect sizes observed in the previous studies. Using MedPower (Kenny, 2017), given sample size ($N = 173$) and alpha set to $\alpha = .05$, our Study 1 had an 82% power to detect an indirect effect of $b = .08$ or higher. While Study 1 might be underpowered to detect weaker effects, such effects are unlikely to be practically meaningful.

All analyses were performed in R (version 4.3.0), using lavaan (Rosseel, 2012), lm.beta (Behrendt, 2023), NCA (Dul, 2023), psych (Revelle, 2023), semTools (Jorgensen et al., 2022), and basic R packages. Data and scripts are available in the Open Science Framework Archive (OSF: https://osf.io/rt4vx/?view_only=7d376f187e1a4bcf8d6bc989724b54c9).

Results

As illustrated in Figure 2, robust relationships appeared between the variables of interest. Creative self-beliefs were associated with project creativity, uncertainty acceptance, adjusting approach, emotion regulation, and readiness for sharing. In line with expectations, we also observed positive links between creative self-regulation and the creativity level of teachers' projects. Specifically, project creativity was significantly linked to uncertainty acceptance, adjusting approach, emotion regulation, and readiness for sharing.

Figure 2

Pearson's Correlations between Project's Creativity, Creative Self-Beliefs, and Self-Regulation Factors along with Variables' Distributions

Note. Variable distributions are shown on the diagonal. The lower triangular area shows correlation coefficients with 95% confidence intervals [CI]; crossed-out squares are nonsignificant. The upper triangular shows point estimates and CIs visually. CSB = creative self-beliefs, OE = obstacle expectations, UA = uncertainty acceptance, AA = adjusting approach, MG = managing and reframing ambiguous goals, ER = emotion regulation and dealing with obstacles, IA = improving approach, RS = readiness for sharing.

Our next step involved a hierarchical regression, with project creativity regressed on creative self-regulation factors introduced to the model in three blocks, corresponding to the phases of project work, i.e., forethought, performance, and self-reflection (Table 2).

Table 2
Creative Self-Regulation as a Predictor of Teachers' Projects' Creativity

Predictors	<i>B</i> (<i>SE</i>)	β
Block 1: Forethought (Model: $F[2, 170] = 6.61, p = .002, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .061$)		
Obstacle Expectations	-0.174 (0.061)	-.255**
Uncertainty Acceptance	0.247 (0.071)	.311***

Block 2: Performance		
(Model $F[5, 167] = 5.11, p < .001, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .107, \Delta R^2 = .05$)		
Adjusting Approach	0.336 (0.118)	.280**
Managing Goals	-0.101 (0.072)	-.110
Emotion Regulation	-0.026 (0.110)	-.024
Block 3: Self-Reflection		
(Model $F[7, 165] = 4.35, p < .001, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .120, \Delta R^2 = .01$)		
Improving Approach	0.065 (0.056)	.092
Readiness for Sharing	0.167 (0.086)	.174#

Note. $N = 173, \#p = .053; *p < .05; **p < .01; ***p < .001$

The creativity of teachers' projects was associated with self-regulation in the forethought phase ($R^2 = .06$), during the process ($\Delta R^2 = .05$), and in the self-reflection phase ($\Delta R^2 = .01$). Teachers who expected more problems before work tended to end up with less creative projects, while uncertainty acceptance was positively associated with project creativity.¹ In the performance phase, creativity was associated with the adjusting approach. Finally, project creativity was marginally associated with teachers' readiness to share its effects ($p = .053$). Overall, these findings are consistent with our H1.

To test H2, we explored if teachers' creative self-beliefs drive self-regulation and project creativity (see Figure 3).

Figure 3

Creative Self-Regulation as a Mediator in the Relationship between Teachers' Creative Self-Beliefs and Their Projects' Creativity

¹ This relationship suggests a suppression, as the regression effect differs from bivariate correlation (see Figure 2), where obstacle expectation was not significantly associated with project creativity. A similar pattern has been observed previously (Zielińska et al., 2023). Therefore, we caution against considering obstacle expectations as a regulatory mechanism that is detrimental to creativity.

Note. All values are standardized regression coefficients. Dark red lines denote ceiling regression-free disposal hull (CR-FDH) effects from the Necessary Condition Analysis. Regression lines and accompanied 95% confidence intervals are presented in the same color as points.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

We obtained a significant indirect effect, $\beta = .085$, $p = .044$, $b = 0.061$, 95% *CI* (0.009, 0.130; standard errors estimated using bootstrapping with 5000 samples). The direct link between the creative self-beliefs and project creativity observed before ($\beta = .356$) decreased to $\beta = .271$, suggesting a partial mediation. Thus, in line with H2, teachers' creative self-beliefs were found to have both direct and indirect (via creative self-regulation) effects on their projects' creativity.

Figure 3 shows quite strong average links between the variables of interest. At the same time, despite the linear relationship, cases are scarce in the upper-left corners of all the scatterplots. Such a relationship is in line with the hypothesized necessary-condition-like pattern. More precisely, a high level of creativity was unlikely if teachers' creative self-beliefs or self-regulation were low. To formally test our hypothesis, we performed the necessary condition analyses to determine whether creative self-beliefs are necessary for creative self-regulation (H3a) and whether both creative self-beliefs and creative self-regulation are necessary for project creativity (H3b).

In the case of the relationship between creative self-beliefs and creative self-regulation, the significance test demonstrated an NCA-like relationship ($p = .019$), with an effect size deemed moderate (CR-FDH $d = .22$) as per Dul's recommendations (Dul, 2016). Thus, teachers' creative self-beliefs were quite strongly associated with creative self-regulation on average ($\beta = .50$), but also their low level made effective self-regulation unlikely, consistently with H3a.

When the relationship between creative self-beliefs and the creativity of teachers' projects was considered, there was not only a statistically significant average effect but also a significant necessary condition-like pattern. The effect size was moderate: CR-FDH $d = .25$, $p = .004$. We discovered a similar NCA-like pattern of association between creative self-regulation and project creativity. The effect size was moderate (CR-FDH $d = .19$) and statistically significant ($p = .021$), denoting that poor creative self-regulation makes creative outcomes implausible. Thus, H3b was also confirmed.

In our final analysis, we utilized latent profile analysis to investigate the different patterns of self-regulatory behavior exhibited by teachers. As there were several regulatory strategies to consider, we tested solutions with up to ten latent profiles. The fit indices and bootstrapped likelihood test suggested a 6-class solution (see SOM Table S3). However, based on the entropy value, a 3-class solution could be considered as well. Therefore, we examined the profiles obtained from 3-, 4-, 5-, and 6-class solutions and ultimately selected a 3-class model for its parsimony (see Figure 4, upper panel); the more complex models added configurations that only differed in the intensity of using regulatory mechanisms, rather than presenting a distinct pattern of strategies (see SOM Figure S1 for more information on alternative models).

The first and smallest class identified (see Figure 4, upper panel) was characterized by *dysregulated* behavior reflected in low levels of all but one regulatory tactic. This group quite accurately expected that the process would be challenging and full of obstacles, yet they struggled to take control of their activity. In contrast, the second class exhibited a *plan-and-execute* approach. The low level of obstacle expectations and anticipating few uncertainties during project realization

suggests that the group had a clearer vision of their projects and carefully planned each work step. Having specific objectives in mind, these teachers did not have to deal with ambiguous goals, and when the project was finished, they saw no need to improve it further. At the same time, they adjusted their approach and regulated emotions during the process and expressed a high readiness to share the effects with others. Finally, the largest group (see Figure 4, upper panel) demonstrated a more flexible *draft-and-revise* approach. Compared to the previous profile, the most apparent differences were visible in the forethought phase. Teachers exhibiting a *draft-and-revise* profile acknowledged the uncertainties of the creative process and expected obstacles to overcome. While they also used other regulatory mechanisms quite intensely, they expressed a lower readiness to share the effects than teachers who adopted a *plan-and-execute* approach (as confirmed by ANOVA, $F(2,170) = 29.62, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .06$, followed by a pairwise comparison: $p = .035$ [Holm's correction], Cohen's $d = 0.380$).

Did teachers who employed various regulatory approaches differ in their projects' creativity and creative self-beliefs? The identified profiles varied significantly regarding project creativity, $F(2,170) = 5.15, p = .007, \eta^2_p = .06$ (see Figure 4, lower left panel). Pairwise comparisons with Holm's correction indicated that teachers who adopted a *draft-and-revise* approach ended up with more creative projects than those exhibiting *dysregulated* behavior ($p = .005, d = 0.61$). The difference between the *plan-and-execute* and *dysregulated* approaches was marginally non-significant ($p = .080, d = 0.41$). There was no difference in the creativity of projects prepared by teachers adopting the *draft-and-revise* and *plan-and-execute* approaches ($p = .273$).

A similar pattern of differences was also observed in terms of creative self-beliefs: $F(2,170) = 16.67, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .16$ (see Figure 4, lower right panel). Teachers who exhibited *dysregulated* behavior reported lower levels of creative self-beliefs compared to *draft-and-revise* ($p < .001, d = -1.04$) and *plan-and-execute* profiles ($p < .001, d = -0.92$): we emphasize large differences between the groups. Once again, the latter two classes did not differ in creative self-beliefs scores ($p = .469$).

Figure 4

Upper panel: Profiles of Self-Regulation Factors in a 3-Class Solution. Lower panels: Differences in Project Creativity (left) and Creative Self-Beliefs (right) Among the Profiles.

Note. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals [CI] for the means. OE = obstacle expectations, UA = uncertainty acceptance, AA = adjusting approach, MG = managing and reframing ambiguous goals, ER = emotion regulation and dealing with obstacles, IA = improving approach, RS = readiness for sharing.

Discussion

Study 1 tested four hypotheses concerning the factors underlying teachers' creativity. First, we were interested if and how teachers' self-regulation predicts whether their projects will be more or less creative. Second, we examined if creative self-beliefs are associated with project creativity and creative self-regulation. Third, we hypothesized that creative self-beliefs might serve as factors that are necessary yet not sufficient for effective self-regulation and that both creative self-beliefs and creative self-regulation are necessary for project creativity. Our findings supported these hypotheses, while person-centered analyses extended our understanding of the mechanisms engaged in teachers' creativity.

Creative self-regulation factors of the forethought phase, obstacle expectations and uncertainty acceptance, explained a unique portion of the variance in project creativity. Interestingly, we found that while teachers open to uncertainty tended to end up with more original projects, expecting obstacles was negatively associated with project creativity. Given the lack of significant bivariate associations and a negative sign of the regression coefficient, it is apparent that a suppression effect occurred here (Paulhus et al., 2004). Given the modest multicollinearity among the predictors ($r_{OE-UA} = .57$), it seems unlikely that the negative link observed in multivariate regression analysis resulted from a statistical artifact. Furthermore, endorsing the negative relationship between obstacle expectations and project creativity would contradict the extensive literature demonstrating how recognizing potential obstacles can strengthen the commitment to a goal and make its attainment more likely (Duckworth et al., 2011; Oettingen et al., 2000).

Thus, we posit that the finding that obstacle expectations and uncertainty acceptance suppress some of each other's variance may also have a more substantial, even if speculative, explanation. The shared variance between uncertainty acceptance and obstacle expectations may indicate an individual's recognition of the uncertain and resource-demanding nature of the creative process, yet with no particular affective response to it. The latter can be captured by the unique parts of the factors. After removing the overlapping variance in a multivariate model, uncertainty acceptance would reflect truly embracing the ill-defined, vague, and dubious character of creative work. This could be why the link between uncertainty acceptance and project creativity ($r = .17$) became more apparent once the shared variance was eliminated ($\beta = .31$). Conversely, the purified obstacle expectation factor would indicate perceiving ambiguities as a handicap or obstacle to being effective. The unique components of both factors could distinguish the response to the evolving creative process: either embracing the risk and anticipating ways to deal with obstacles proactively (i.e., purified uncertainty acceptance) or feeling discouraged and intimidated by the forthcoming work (i.e., purified obstacle expectation). If that is the case, the negative association between obstacle expectation and project creativity observed in regression analysis appears reasonable:

teachers who understood the demands of the creative process but felt overwhelmed from the outset could not manage the work effectively and eventually ended up with less creative projects.

Of the performance phase dimensions, adjusting the work to the task's demands was the main predictor of the projects' creativity. Therefore, successful self-regulation during this period hinges on timely responding to new ideas, opportunities, and obstacles by adapting work strategies accordingly. This likely requires rich metacognitive resources to be engaged: from metacognitive knowledge (e.g., knowing what strategies proved effective in the past; see Lebuda & Benedek, 2023; Metallidou, 2009) to monitoring and evaluating one's processes (Bowling et al., 2022) to making mental shifts (e.g., replacing simple strategies with more complex and effective ones; see Gilhooly et al., 2007). This engagement can provide a more realistic view of the progress made, what else needs to be done, and how to accomplish it, thus activating behavioral change and strengthening goal pursuit (Oettingen & Reininger, 2016).

In the self-reflection phase, project creativity was marginally linked with the readiness for sharing. Thus, teachers eager to present their projects to others obtained more creative effects (note that the bivariate association was statistically significant). At first sight, this might seem tautological: teachers were satisfied and happily shared their projects, as the projects were creative. Still, the pattern observed speaks in favor of teachers' metacognitive accuracy (e.g., Pesout & Nietfeld, 2021). The significant correlation ($r = .29$) between teachers' willingness to share their project outcomes and the independently judged creativity of those projects demonstrates that their eagerness was justified. Presumably, teachers who were enthusiastic about sharing their work were aware of its quality, and their self-assessment aligned with the judges' ratings.

Additionally, we observed a robust bivariate association between teachers' creative self-beliefs and their projects' creativity ($r = .36$). Previous studies demonstrated that creative self-beliefs predict creative activity and achievement (Lebuda et al., 2021) while being less systematically linked to cognitive measures of creativity (Haase et al., 2018; Pretz & McCollum, 2014). The relationship

between self-beliefs and achievement is reciprocal: success builds confidence, and confidence translates into success.

Importantly, though, the role of self-beliefs might also be indirect. People who are convinced that they can function creatively set bolder goals and use more adaptive strategies while approaching them (Bandura, 1997, 2001). We found that teachers' creative self-beliefs were associated with creative self-regulation, thus both directly and indirectly informing the level of creativity. This finding aligns with previous results (Zielińska et al., 2022) and contributes to the Creative Behavior as Agentic Action (CBAA) model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019), which underlines the importance of self-perceptions in converting creative potential into behavior. Notably, our analysis suggested not only that creative self-regulation mediates the relationship between creative self-beliefs and project creativity, but also that there is a necessary-condition-like pattern. Low creative self-beliefs and poor self-regulation made accomplishing creative projects highly unlikely. At the same time, while high creative self-beliefs or creative self-regulation made creative outcomes much more plausible, they were in no way sufficient.

Finally, this study applied a person-centered approach to distill the specific patterns of regulatory behavior among teachers (see the left part of Figure 5 for the profiles' summary). The first profile represents teachers who struggled with managing their work and exhibited a *dysregulated* approach. Of the seven mechanisms analyzed, they tended to present only obstacle expectations, which may indicate feeling overwhelmed with navigating the project rather than thinking of effective ways to cope with its demands. Feeling intimidated by the creative process, they disengaged from monitoring and regulating the activity and ended up with the least creative projects. One of the potential sources of poor self-regulation among this group could be their low level of creative self-beliefs, at least when compared to the remaining profiles. Indeed, as our analyses demonstrated, creative self-beliefs fueled self-regulation, thus supporting teachers in preparing more creative projects.

Another group of teachers tended to adopt a *plan-and-execute* approach. Low regulatory mechanisms of the forethought phase suggest that this group had a clear vision for their projects, leaving less room for unpredicted problems and expecting fewer obstacles. With a vivid idea, they pursued specific objectives rather than struggled with ambiguous goals. During the performance, they regulated their emotions and adjusted their approach. However, their final effects were likely as they initially envisioned, resulting in “accomplished opuses” that, in teachers’ eyes, required no further refinement and would yield the same result if repeated. Notably, this group was eager to share their work with others, and their enthusiasm was accurate: their projects were evaluated as highly creative by expert judges. This is an intriguing finding, given the clear-cut character of this regulatory approach. Although a *plan-and-execute* approach resembles a well-defined goal pursuit, with less room for revising ideas and restrategizing (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017), it aligns well with teachers’ creative endeavors.

In contrast, the *draft-and-revise* profile was characterized by more dynamic and responsive actions. During the forethought phase, teachers of this group employed regulatory tactics that were quite the opposite of those in the *plan-and-execute* configuration. They acknowledged uncertainties, anticipated obstacles, and saw their initial ideas as a starting point for future modifications and revisions. Rather than expecting project execution, they expected its evolution. Consequently, they applied all regulatory mechanisms to respond to project demands adequately: adjusted their ways of working, set goals while acknowledging ambiguity, and managed emotions to sustain efforts. Even when the work was finished, they were still able to recognize what could be done differently or better. Although the outcome was already there, they tended to see the project as *never completed* (Botella, 2013) and as a source of inspiration. Perhaps this is why they were less willing to share the effect with others than *planners-and-executers*. This is not to say they were not satisfied or proud of what they achieved; they instead saw a path of further development and were ready to follow it. Nevertheless, their projects were assessed by judges as very creative, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the *draft-and-revise* approach.

Additionally, our results revealed an important pattern: the projects obtained with *plan-and-execute* and *draft-and-revise* approaches did not differ in terms of judges' scores. We see these null results as a fascinating illustration of equifinality (e.g., Bissola et al., 2014) in the creativity context, which highlights how a given endpoint can be reached through different pathways. As our results demonstrate, there is no universal scenario for how to arrive at creative outcomes within educational settings, and it might be crucial for teachers to discover the methods that best suit them and their students.

Limitations

The results of Study 1 should be read with certain limitations kept in mind. We believe that three of these are particularly important. First, given our relatively modest ($N = 173$) sample of teachers, these are initial findings, so replications are essential.

The second limitation is associated with the correlational nature of Study 1, which makes causal claims unwarranted. Given the reciprocity of the effects, the proposed mediation model should be considered preliminary. We cannot refute that teachers who conducted more creative projects started considering themselves more creative, and so their confidence grew. Still, the question remains: how and why did they engage in creative projects in the first place? The logic of our model aligns here with sociocognitive theorizing, which highlights the critical role of motivational factors, including self-beliefs, in self-regulatory competency and their contribution to achievement outcomes (see Schunk & Zimmerman, 2007 for an extensive overview).

Third and finally, we acknowledge that Study 1 employed a somewhat static and *doubly retrospective* measurement of self-regulation. Teachers described what happened while they worked on a project and reported how they planned their activities, conducted them, and reacted when the project was done. Although such a design has been effectively implemented in previous investigations (Zielińska et al., 2022, 2023), recalling and reporting all aspects of the creative work could be challenging. Therefore, to replicate and extend our findings in more naturalistic and dynamic surroundings, we decided to conduct Study 2.

Figure 5

The Summary of Regulatory Profiles Identifies in Study 1 (left column) and Further Explored in Study 2 (right column)

PROFILE	STATIC SELF-REGULATORY PATTERNS	DYNAMIC SELF- AND CO-REGULATORY PATTERNS
PLAN-EXECUTE APPROACH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Viewing the creative process as smooth, unproblematic (\downarrowOE), and predictable (\downarrowUA). Staying open to opportunities and adjusting the approach when necessary (\uparrowAA), while keeping the initial main goals stable (\downarrowMG) and sustaining motivation to achieve them (\uparrowER). Being satisfied with the outcome without needing further refinement (\downarrowIA) and enthusiastically sharing the results with others (\uparrowRS). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflecting on one's own competencies to guide the creative process (<i>Utilizing personal expertise</i>). Ensuring students grasp the essence of the project at hand (<i>Introducing and expanding the topic to students</i>) and establishing clear working guidelines (<i>Organizational activities</i>). Exploring various ideas, aiming for a detailed plan, and mitigating uncertainties in the process (<i>Simulations and final vision refinement</i>) to smoothly implement the vision rather than improvising (<i>Readiness to modify ideas flexibly</i>). Acknowledging the project's practical applications (<i>Focus on product strengths</i>) and being eager to showcase it to the public (<i>Excitement about idea sharing</i>).
DRAFT-REVISE APPROACH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognizing the complexities of the creative process (\uparrowOE) and being conscious of its unpredictable nature (\uparrowUA). Modifying both goals (\uparrowMG) and methods of achieving them (\uparrowAA) flexibly, while keeping an eye on emotional and motivational resources (\uparrowER). Seeing potential enhancements in the results, using them as inspiration for future projects (\uparrowIA); showing a moderate willingness—when compared to the plan-execute approach—to display the outcome publicly (\uparrowRS). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drawing inspiration from everyday classroom challenges (<i>Being driven by the idea</i>). Attentively responding to student initiatives, ideas, and interests, and recalibrating expectations as needed (<i>Following students' reactions and needs</i>). Acknowledging potential challenges, thereby avoiding rigid assumptions about the final outcome or the path to it (<i>Simulations and final vision refinement</i>). Experimenting with diverse solutions, expanding upon ideas, and collaboratively deciding on the next steps with students (<i>Readiness to modify ideas flexibly</i>). Valuing the versatility of the project (<i>Focus on product strengths</i>) and an eagerness to inspire others through the results (<i>Excitement about idea sharing</i>).
DYSREGULATED APPROACH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expecting the creative process to be demanding (\uparrowOE) yet struggling to embrace its challenges (\downarrowUA). Lacking the means to adapt to changing circumstances (\downarrowAA), set goals (\downarrowMG), and handle the emotional burden (\downarrowER). Feeling dissatisfied with the results and hesitant to share them with others (\downarrowRS), without recognizing potential improvements (\downarrowIA). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crafting a project plan but becoming overwhelmed by the anticipated challenges (<i>Simulations and final vision refinement</i>). Gradually simplifying the project to increase the chances for its completion (<i>Readiness to modify ideas flexibly</i>). Underscoring the simplicity of the final product as its strength (<i>Focus on product strengths</i>) yet expressing discontent over not meeting initial expectations (<i>Excitement about idea sharing</i>).

Note. OE = obstacle expectations, UA = uncertainty acceptance, AA = adjusting approach, MG = managing and reframing ambiguous goals, ER = emotion regulation and dealing with obstacles, IA = improving approach, RS = readiness for sharing.

Study 2

Study 2 aimed to provide a more dynamic overview of teachers' self-regulation while working on a creative project: collaboratively developing a new educational aid with students over nearly three months. We adopted a convergent mixed methods design, in which quantitative and qualitative data were first collected and analyzed separately, and then integrated (McCrudden et al., 2019). Through synthesizing quantitative and qualitative insights, steered by narrative integration (Fetters et al., 2013), we focused on a nuanced depiction of teachers' creative self-regulation within dynamic settings.

In the quantitative strand, we examined how the intensity of using self-regulatory mechanisms changed over ten weeks of project realization. Further, we investigated whether more intensified project involvement entailed a stronger regulatory approach, namely, whether dedicating more time to work corresponded to heightened self-regulatory efforts. Finally, like in Study 1, we also explored if self-regulation is associated with higher creativity of the effects obtained, assessed by teachers in terms of originality and usefulness.

Then, during the qualitative part of Study 2, we sought a better understanding of teachers' creative self-regulation at different stages of the work. What specific regulatory behaviors did teachers employ when conceptualizing the project, during its development, and after submitting the accomplished educational aid? How were students involved in the whole process? Finally, did the teachers' approaches resemble the plan-execute, draft-revise, or dysregulated profiles identified in Study 1? These were the central research questions that informed our qualitative analyses.

Method

Participants

Sixteen teachers participated in the quantitative and qualitative parts of Study 2, with no overlap with the participants from Study 1. This sample comprised a unique group of teachers who entered a competition to co-create an educational aid with their students. Thus, while in Study 1, teachers themselves identified the project that spurred their creative engagement, and their implicit

definitions of creativity likely informed this choice (Gralewski & Karwowski, 2018), Study 2 was set in the context explicitly designed to require creative involvement.

The quantitative part was carried out over ten weeks, and teachers responded every week. The overall response rate at the measurement level (every week) was 60%. The dataset had a multilevel structure: the responses were clustered within participants, so the final database contained 87 interdependent records. After completing the work (but before announcing the competition results), the same teachers—representing ten teams that qualified for the competition finals—participated in in-depth interviews.

Competition

Study 2 was conducted in the context of the “Science for you” competition organized by the Copernicus Science Center in Poland (see <https://www.kopernik.org.pl/en>). The competition aims to enhance teachers’ knowledge in developing educational aids and spark students’ scientific curiosity. Contestants are teams of 4-5 primary school students (from one or multiple grades) supervised by one or two teachers. The task for the competition is to design and craft an educational aid, and apply it during classroom sessions. Additionally, participants are expected to produce a 5-minute video documenting the entire tool development process. The educational aid should be an original piece that showcases phenomena from natural or exact sciences and addresses issues commonly faced in the classroom, school, or local community.

In the first stage of the competition, teachers submitted a brief written description of the educational aid they intended to co-develop with their students. The competition’s jury—scientific experts, teacher specialists, and government representatives—selected ten teams to advance to the finals. The selection was based on the following criteria: the project’s alignment with current scientific knowledge, student involvement in creating the educational aid, the project’s feasibility and originality, its relevance in a school setting, and its pedagogical value. In the next stage, the final teams worked on developing their tools over ten weeks. After evaluating the documentary videos detailing the projects, the jury identified five laureate teams that excelled in both scientific and

educational aspects (the same set of criteria as used in the initial stage was applied). No specific ranking order was assigned to the laureates.

Figure 6 shows examples of projects developed by teacher-student teams as part of the competition. All ten finalists' projects, accompanied by brief descriptions and videos of their development, can be found in the SOM (Figure S2).

Figure 6

Examples of Educational Aids Created by Teacher–Student Teams as Part of the “Science For You” Competition

“Neuron with electricity”

This teaching aid is an electric circuit installed on a wooden board to demonstrate how the reflex arc functions. By constructing the model and learning how it works, students have the opportunity to manipulate it and mimic the mechanisms of the nervous system.

“Magnetic Rollercoaster”

This scientific model is based on a linear motor that generates a magnetic force to move a trolley made with batteries and magnets. With this aid, students can test whether the trolley can jump over an obstacle, determine the maximum height of the rollercoaster, and explore the various factors that affect magnetic strength, such as battery type, coil turns, magnet size, etc.

Measures

Creative Self-Regulation. Teachers' regulatory mechanisms employed throughout the project were measured using a creative self-regulation questionnaire similar to that in Study 1, but adapted for the dynamic context of the competition. Teachers responded to the questionnaire weekly and, before answering, identified the phase they were in during that week (forethought, performance, or self-reflection). Short descriptions of the phases were provided to assist in this decision. In the forethought phase, participants responded to seven items corresponding to the self-regulation factors of obstacle expectations and uncertainty acceptance. In the performance phase, they were presented with items measuring adjusting approach, managing goals, and emotion regulation. In the self-reflection phase, they responded to six items corresponding to improving approach and readiness for sharing. We used an overall weekly self-regulation score as the primary

variable of interest in our analysis: we first averaged the responses for each self-regulation factor within a given phase and then derived an overall average from those scores.

Time Spent Working on the Project. In each week assigned to the forethought or performance phase, teachers identified the number of hours they spent working on the project. The question about time was not asked if participants had completed the work.

The Creativity of the Project. Using a seven-point Likert scale (*1 = not at all, 7 = definitely yes*), each week, participants assessed to what extent their idea or finished product was original and useful in a class. Given that these indexes were robustly interrelated ($\alpha = .85$), we averaged them to obtain an aggregated measure of (self-assessed) creativity of the project. To examine the validity of this index, in a multilevel model, we predicted originality, usefulness, and the aggregated creativity index by participants' status (*0 = other, 1 = laureates*) obtained at the end of the competition. As presented in the SOM (see Table S4), laureates provided higher ratings, confirming the validity of the project's self-assessed creativity.

Procedure and Data Analysis

The overall scheme of our mixed-method study design and procedures is illustrated in Figure 7. The quantitative part of Study 2 was microlongitudinal: it lasted for ten weeks, during which teachers co-worked on their projects with students and completed online surveys weekly. Given the clustered nature of our quantitative database, with time points nested within teachers, we relied on multilevel models. Multilevel modeling is known to handle missing data effectively (Silvia et al., 2014), which makes it especially suitable given our design and moderate level of missingness. Our quantitative analyses explored two main questions. First, we were interested in changes in teachers' creative self-regulation across weeks and the relationship between the overall time spent on a project and creative self-regulation. Second, our focal research question explored the dynamic relationship between creative self-regulation each week and project creativity. All analyses were performed in R (version 4.3.0) using lme4 (Bates et al., 2015) package.

The qualitative part was based on in-depth interviews, to which all sixteen finalists were invited. Since some teams involved two teachers while others only had one, we conducted either dyadic interviews (6 instances) or individual interviews (4 instances). Initially, participants were briefed about the study's objectives, their voluntary involvement, and the possibility to withdraw at any time. They also gave consent for the interviews to be recorded. Before the analysis, all interviews were transcribed, yielding 232 pages of standard manuscript (min = 7.08; max = 44.03; M = 23.2; SD = 11.9).

The interviews were semi-structured and centered around the self-regulatory aspects of project realization across phases. Firstly, we asked teachers about their thoughts and actions in the initial, preparatory stage, focusing on sources of inspiration and envisioned project outcomes. Then, we delved into how the ideas were implemented, the evolution of the project, the challenges faced, and the factors that helped teachers maintain their efforts. Lastly, teachers were prompted to reflect on finalizing the project, articulate their insights on the process behind tool development, and evaluate the obtained outcomes. The specific questions asked regarding the forethought, performance, and self-reflection phases are illustrated in Figure 7 (right panel). A detailed interview protocol is included in the SOM (Table S5).

We applied qualitative thematic analysis to identify the themes in teachers' interviews (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Although no coding scheme was defined a priori, the focus on self-regulatory mechanisms and the phase-based interview structure guided our coding procedure. We were particularly interested in providing a detailed description of teachers' self-regulation at different project stages and the extent of student involvement. To achieve this, we analyzed the data through the lens of self-regulation profiles identified in Study 1, searching for indications of these overarching strategies. Informed by these objectives, the second author performed an iterative analysis of the transcripts, carried out initial coding, and developed a codebook to accurately capture the regulatory aspects of the project realization. Then, the first and third authors verified and supplemented the proposed list of codes. All newly emerging codes were discussed by the research team. The coding

process ended when the codebook was data-saturated and redundancies were resolved. After establishing the final list of codes, we combined them into overarching interpretation themes. Figure 8 presents a complete coding scheme.

Figure 7
Mixed Methods Study Design Adopted in Study 2

Figure 8
Complete Coding Scheme for the Qualitative Part of Study 2

PHASE	INTERPRETATION THEMES	CODES	EXEMPLARY VERBATIMS
FORETHOUGHT	Being driven by the idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Frustration due to lack of educational aids ▪ Need for original educational aids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>These two subjects highlighted our need for something new; we discussed what was missing in each.</i> ▪ <i>While the aid was interesting, it lacked originality. We were seeking something innovative and unconventional.</i>
	Following students' reactions and needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Relaxed plan to empower students' creative agency ▪ Following students' enthusiasm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>It wasn't rigidly planned; students played a significant role, implementing their ideas based on our lessons.</i> ▪ <i>When someone suggested an idea, there was a spark in their eyes saying, 'Let's do that'.</i>
	Utilizing personal expertise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrating expertise from both teachers ▪ Using knowledge from previous competitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>We chose the eye's accommodation, bridging biology and physics, allowing us to combine our expertise.</i> ▪ <i>Our first project ranked low, but now we're in the finals again, showing our growth and experience.</i>
	Introducing and expanding the topic to students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhancing student knowledge on the topic ▪ Clarifying project goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>We didn't tell them how it should work; they had to figure it out and research. We just gave hints.</i> ▪ <i>At the start, I propose an idea, and we discuss it. Students suggest changes, and I'm open to shift the direction.</i>
	Organizational activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing rules of work ▪ Outlining competition rules and regulations ▪ Assessing students' interests and competencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>We set a specific day for this, ensuring it was when our science club met, to better fit the students' schedule.</i> ▪ <i>At the meeting, I outlined the competition rules, emphasized the prizes, and shared a rollercoaster video.</i> ▪ <i>We asked students for their ideas on educational aids and what they'd like to create.</i>
	Simulations and final vision refinement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exploring multiple ideas and solutions ▪ Finalizing product vision ▪ Anticipation of problems and obstacles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>After brainstorming, we turned to students for input, and they later experimented with ideas.</i> ▪ <i>We first sketched it out on a paper... But I had a different vision in mind; it's different when you visualize it.</i> ▪ <i>Though simple, it's time-consuming. When students take over, it takes even longer—I didn't anticipate that.</i>
PERFORMANCE	Readiness to modify ideas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Elaboration (technical, aesthetical, functional) ▪ Augmenting project functionality ▪ Reducing project complexity ▪ Readiness to test alternatives ▪ Negotiating with students and co-teacher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Things kept changing because certain aspects didn't work or were technically unfeasible.</i> ▪ <i>Changes came fluidly, arising from practical needs or new ideas.</i> ▪ <i>Originally, it was meant to be more intricate, but we had to simplify and scale down due to limitations.</i> ▪ <i>With some extra resources, we started adding new features and trying out alternatives.</i> ▪ <i>She had her initial vision, and when shopping, I saw more of her ideas. Yet, everyone had slightly different expectations, differing from the final result.</i>
SELF-REFLECTION	Recognizing product strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Appreciation of product simplicity and versatility ▪ Appreciation of product safety and usability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>I understand it might be used simply; a student just connects the wires, does a quick test, and gets results.</i> ▪ <i>Our school has many corridors and stairs, so they smartly added wheels; their ingenuity always surprised us.</i>
	Excitement about idea sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Seeking opportunities for idea sharing ▪ Displaying product in a visible place ▪ Willingness to share the product with others ▪ Sense of pride in the product ▪ Motivation to inspire others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>The students wanted to showcase it to their peers.</i> ▪ <i>I imagined that if they want to display our product, it must be visually appealing and quickly demonstrable.</i> ▪ <i>We didn't want it to be shown only once a year. It had to be practical and not just a bulky one-time display.</i> ▪ <i>When the principal praised the students, I was ecstatic. They felt important.</i> ▪ <i>A nice motivator was the continuous interest of students, teachers, and even our IT guy.</i>

Results

Creative Self-Regulation in Weekly Snapshots: Results of the Quantitative Part of Study 2

A multilevel model with self-regulation as a dependent variable and subsequent weeks as a factor yielded a statistically significant effect ($F[9, 64.48] = 3.75, p < .001$). The trend resembled the shape of an inverted J: self-regulation first increased markedly (and significantly), to begin to decrease slightly in the final phases of work (Figure 9, panel A). Particularly noteworthy is the increase visible after the 3rd week, when participants moved from planning to implementing the tasks they set for their teams. Also, time spent on the project each week predicted self-regulation ($b = 0.20, 95\% \text{ CI: } [0.13, 0.28], p < .001$) (Figure 9, panel B).

Figure 9

The Relationship Between the Time Spent on Project Work and Self-Regulation (Panel A) and Changes Over Time (Weeks of Study 2) in Self-Regulation (Panel B).

Note. The gray box around the black line indicates 95% confidence intervals around the estimated fixed effect. Thin colored lines show the results of individual teachers.

Again—in line with Study 1, albeit here in more dynamic settings—there appeared to be a statistically significant and robust positive effect of self-regulation on project creativity, $b = 0.28, 95\% \text{ CI: } [0.06, 0.51], p = .014$ (see Figure 10).

Figure 10

Relations Between Self-Regulation and Perceived Creativity

Diving Deeper: Results of the Qualitative Part of Study 2

While the quantitative results highlighted the pivotal role of effectively directing one's actions for project creativity and noted time-dependent shifts in these efforts, these findings only partially illuminate the nuances of the creative process. The actual experience of developing the educational tool, the particular circumstances spurring self-regulatory efforts, and their impact on the project progress remain to be fully explored. Moreover, the quantitative results may inadvertently conflate teachers' and students' regulation, overlooking both unique teacher-driven processes and collaborative regulatory efforts.

Therefore, our interviews aimed to delve deeper into teachers' self-regulation, offering a more dynamic perspective. We examined the specific content of their approach across the forethought, performance, and self-reflection phases. Furthermore, prompted by the results of Study 1, we explored whether teachers displayed and varied in overarching regulatory patterns. In particular, we were looking for any representations of self-regulation profiles—characterized as plan-execute, draft-revise, or dysregulated approaches—in teachers' responses to open-ended questions about the project. Knowing each team's competition status, i.e., whether they were declared laureates or not, we aimed to discern regulatory actions associated with award recognition. Lastly, considering the different nature of creative projects across the studies—with Study 1 focusing

specifically on teacher-led projects and Study 2 emphasizing teamwork—our qualitative data analysis also sought insights into teacher-student interactions in regulating creative action.

Regulation in the Forethought Phase. Fourteen codes, grouped under six interpretation themes, were identified to describe the preparatory stage of the project (see Figure 8). Broadly speaking, teachers discussed their inspirations for tool development, personal experiences they drew upon, methods of organizing their own and students' work, clarifying competition goals, envisioning project outcomes, and student-driven modifications to the initial plan. While these themes emerged consistently across all interviews, the frequency of their appearance varied, suggesting profile-like tendencies. Below, we unpack the observed patterns, highlighting examples of the diverse approaches taken by teachers (see Figure 5 for a summary).

When searching for an idea and defining the problem, teachers scarcely mentioned a lack of ideas as an issue. Instead, they felt motivated to address some longstanding problems—especially those encountered during everyday teaching—and “they follow their lead.” While some emphasized the necessity of a holistic vision to steer the entire tool development process, others highlighted the value of a more detailed (yet flexible) plan to ensure a successful outcome. These two approaches correspond closely with the draft-revise and plan-execute profiles distinguished in Study 1.

In the beginning, we created a base, a skeleton in this application, and we built on this skeleton. But it was not like everything was strictly planned out there, what was going to happen, because a big role here was played by students, who implemented their ideas in practice based on what we presented to them in theoretical lessons conducted via Zoom, from the physical, biological side. There were meetings; there were also simulations in the Tinkercad program (...).

I think the main concept remained unchanged from the beginning to the end. So, the issue here was more technical, like which plants to choose, how to arrange them properly. However, I believe that the core of this plan remained the same throughout.

When looking for an idea to implement, most teachers focused on choosing an action that fostered the development of students' creativity. The initial decision was often influenced by their enthusiasm and curiosity, which either affirmed the teachers' confidence in the chosen idea or—when lacking—indicated a potential need for change. Additionally, teachers who formulated a more

detailed project plan also leaned on their own expertise, as well as that of their co-teachers, to guide preparations and set goals. However, interactions with students were crucial in formulating project objectives. Their initiatives, ideas, and interests often prompted teachers to recalibrate their expectations or inspired the search for more original and bold concepts:

Because it's like this, we think very stereotypically, we have our experiences, our ideas, something we've already done. And based on our own experiences, we want to do it this way and that, but then it turns out that our idea can be thrown into fairy tales because it doesn't work at all at that moment. Children have a very relaxed and creative approach to this, fresh and not clichéd. From my field of arts, I had an idea to make some part of the decoration, and then the girls come and say: "Ma'am, it should be done this way and that." And I immediately shut up, I didn't even tell them what I had in mind because I decided that my idea was pointless, that's how it goes with them.

Once the general idea for the educational aid was settled, most teachers focused on substantive development and presentation of the project topic to their team members. Frequently, the teacher-leaders sought to expand and organize students' knowledge in the project field, even investing their own time to learn by consulting challenging aspects with external experts. These activities helped clarify possible ambiguities and enabled presenting the problem in the most understandable form. Interestingly, this approach to project preparation tended to be quite universal: employed by both teachers who thoroughly planned and those more inclined to adjust their vision as they proceeded.

In several teams, organizational activities were emphasized during the forethought phase, resonating with the plan-execute approach identified in Study 1. However, while in Study 1, we speculated on teachers' planning tendencies based on low expectations of obstacles and limited acceptance of uncertainty, here we can distinguish the specific organizational steps taken. These included briefing students on the competition regulations, establishing cooperation guidelines, planning the working schedule, discussing necessary materials, and analyzing potential costs. Sometimes, teachers also sought to identify team members' competencies and interests, and distribute tasks accordingly.

The representation of the plan-execute profile was even more pronounced in the last theme identified, *simulations and final vision refinement*. While it surfaced across all teams, some teachers—in collaboration with their students—engaged particularly deeply in crafting a detailed project framework. They determined the final product’s critical functionalities by estimating students’ abilities and the feasibility of the proposed steps. To further evaluate the project plan, they conducted simulations, testing possible solution variants. Through this approach, they attempted to make the tool’s envisioned design as precise as possible and set the stage for a smooth, predictable, modification-free implementation. Thus, they carried out simulations, produced mock-ups, and photographed various iterations of proposed solutions. Eventually, their preparatory steps led them to anticipate the process devoid of bigger challenges and obstacles, again resonating with the characteristics of the plan-execute approach.

First, we drew it out on a long piece of paper, using circles to mark what plants could be where. I adopted a vision of the organization that assumed it could be done in a completely different way. Because you can draw things on a small piece of paper, but then it could turn out that there are too few or too many plants. When I had a 1:1 cardboard box the same length as our box, it was easier. When we went to the store, we set it up in front of the store, one by one, to see which way things would fit.

The organization of the competition fostered the development of self-regulatory competencies related to the preparation stage, as if “necessitating planning and anticipation.” For groups less content with the final result, inadequate project preparation was often seen as the main reason. This sentiment was particularly evident in the reflection of a teacher whose team, as the only one, tended to exhibit a dysregulated approach throughout the project:

Q: Looking back, would you change anything about working on the project?

A: I think probably yes, probably some organizational issues regarding better definition of the goal, deadlines, and realizing why we are doing something, some elements of this whole project, and also doing things somewhat more consciously together with the students.

Teachers who expressed dissatisfaction over not meeting initial expectations concluded that future endeavors would benefit from improved planning, clearer goal-setting, precise deadline formulation, and ensuring that students fully comprehend the project’s vision and meaning. Thus,

after reflecting on the completed creative process, these teachers appeared to see the merits of a plan-execute approach. In particular, they hoped to make the process more predictable by reducing uncertainties and obstacles stemming from a lack of project comprehension. Notably, those who actually aligned with a plan-execute profile indeed recognized that an in-depth understanding of the project's expected outcomes was crucial for students to grasp the tool's purpose and to develop it successfully.

Regulation in the Performance Phase. When discussing their approach during the performance phase, teachers expressed differing levels of *readiness to modify ideas* (five secondary codes; see Figure 8). They engaged with varied intensity in exploring new concepts and solutions, expanding the tool functionality, elaborating on the project scope, or—quite the opposite—reducing its complexity. This phase also underscored the pivotal role of interactions within teams, as dialogue with students or co-teachers often guided the decision to either stick to the plan or redirect actions. These differences observed across the teams again correspond well with the characteristics of the plan-execute and draft-revise profiles identified in Study 1 (see Figure 5).

Teachers who largely adhered to their initial vision recollected fewer obstacles faced during idea implementation. Still, even if situations did not necessitate goal revisions or tactical adjustments, they recognized the value of reacting flexibly to challenges and remained open to possible modifications. When alterations did occur, however, they usually covered project details or specific organizational settings rather than central components of the tool design. Overall, for those teachers, the process of tool development was remembered as progressing seamlessly (“the work was, all in all, light, easy, and pleasant”), aligning exactly with the expected outcomes.

I think everything went smoothly for us with these preparations; we had a pretty well-developed idea for the educational aid and all the things we needed. So once we listed what was specifically required, we just needed to find where to get it, and for a price that would fit within the grant we received. But it all went quite efficiently. We also had a lot of help from two gentlemen at our school, those who helped with everything, so they were very involved and helped attach all the pipes, and painted them, so everything went smoothly, surprisingly well.

Q: Looking back, would you change anything about working on this project?

A: I think not, because we achieved what we intended to.

While some teachers indeed described this phase as unfolding smoothly, without any major conceptual changes, most acknowledged that ideas for developing the aid evolved during the work, echoing the draft-revise tendencies. They declared their propensity for spontaneous actions and testing alternative solutions, often prompted by the encountered obstacles or inspired by students' new ideas. Some activities were aimed at improving the product but also encouraging students to experiment and explore ways of developing their ideas:

Everything changed during the course of the project, because, for example, something did not work, something had to be improved, or, for instance, we thought that something could be done a certain way, but it turned out that it was completely impossible because technically we were unable to do it.

Interestingly, teachers who aligned with the plan-execute profile, believing that the final effect matched the initial expectations and required minimal revisions, eventually received poorer competition evaluations, i.e., were not recognized as laureates. In contrast, those who declared making numerous changes throughout the project and gravitated toward a draft-revise approach received a competition award. The modifications they introduced involved two main strategies: expanding upon or abandoning certain elements. These strategies were usually intertwined rather than employed selectively, and teachers frequently alternated between them.

The first strategy applied involved expanding the project's functionality. While discussing it with students, suggestions arose to add more elements, allowing for a broader use of the teaching aid. The laureates pointed out that the final effect went far beyond their initial plans and evolved from a simple concept to something much more intricate. While the idea was often enriched during the process, sometimes certain improvements were considered and later abandoned. Once the key tool features were ensured, the laureate teams moved to product refinement. The elaborations were technical (adding new elements), aesthetic (the product was decorated), and functional: the product was altered to become more convenient and safer for transport, storage, and presentation. Such modifications often continued until the very end of the project.

The second strategy for introducing changes was to give up on elements that did not work. The decision to abandon certain features often resulted from financial or time constraints, or to ensure the feasibility and safety of the product. In one instance, where the teacher's reminiscences echoed a dysregulated profile from Study 1, reducing project's complexity was driven not by the strive for improvement but rather to increase the chances of even completing the project.

Regulation in the Self-reflection Phase. Teachers' reflections related to project completion fell under two broad themes (see Figure 8): *Recognizing product strengths* (two secondary codes) and *Excitement about idea sharing* (five secondary codes). When evaluating the finished project, teachers did not focus much on its technical limitations or their disappointment with its final appearance. Instead, much more attention was paid to describing the strengths of the proposed product. Importantly, teachers acknowledged the merits of their educational aids regardless of their team's competition status (i.e., laureate or not). However, those who eventually received a prize identified a broader and more diverse range of strengths. On the one hand, the primary perceived advantage of the designed aids was their applicability and broad potential use, suitable for teachers from different disciplines. On the other, the design's technical aspects, such as safety and usability, were appreciated, making the tool easily integrated into daily school routines.

All teachers were excited to present their aid to a broader audience: to other teachers and students, to the local community, or even nationally. Students usually shared this excitement, which further boosted teachers' pride in what had been accomplished and learned. Only one team, which tended to exhibit a dysregulated approach during the forethought and performance phases, was slightly less enthusiastic about sharing. Still, their satisfaction from being able to finalize the project was evident. In contrast, the laureates were eager to share their educational aid with others and display the results in a visible place. The drive to showcase their work stemmed not only from pride in the job done, but also from a desire to inspire others and share the practical use of the outcome:

Not only that, they had an excellent idea to present it to all their classmates on the last day of school, so there was also a lesson that the students taught, starting with biology, that is, with neurons and the nervous system, and ending up with how this nervous system works based on the example of a model that they made themselves. So that I am impressed because it started

with a simple “primitive” thing, adapted to the capabilities of children, and ended up as something simply beautiful. When I say this now, I get chills and goosebumps because it seems to me that it is lovely.

Motivation to Take on the Challenge: The Role of Creative Self-Beliefs. While the interview protocol did not explicitly address teachers’ self-perceptions, their motivational value became apparent during our qualitative analysis. Specifically, the desire to check, confirm, and strengthen one’s own agency was a compelling force behind the creative activity and the very decision to enter the competition. Most teachers saw this challenge as an opportunity to test their competencies and pursue their passion for education. As one of them pointed out:

I love some competitions; I love to go beyond my comfort zone and expand my possibilities.

The initiative responded to the need to face challenges, to look for opportunities for innovative action in working with students, and to create teaching aids that are novel and more attractive than those previously available. The aspect of testing one’s own skills was especially emphasized by novice teachers; the “proving themselves” element motivated them to participate in the competition and continue working through challenging moments. At the same time, it underscored the importance of creativity in teachers’ professional self-image, resonating with the often-expressed sentiment: “I am such a [creative] person.”

Equally crucial in motivating teachers to participate in the initiative was the opportunity to build a sense of efficacy for their team members. Indeed, they focused not so much on the possibility of winning the competition but on providing experiences to develop students’ creativity. As many teachers emphasized, the competition allowed students to succeed, thus strengthening their creative confidence beyond knowledge-based tasks more typical in school settings:

Even if we are not able to win first place in the Board of Education’s competition, where there are only pure tests, I thought to myself: this competition shows creativity and commitment. At the same time, these tasks for children were so varied that everyone could find a little piece for themselves. Some children just started to create this educational aid; there were others who prototyped it, and others who took part in the recording, because some did not want to. So I think you can be good at different things and there does not have to be the kind of test that gets filled out, and if someone is a laureate of such a competition testing their knowledge, that does not mean that he or she is excellent in this field.

Integration and Discussion

Study 2 replicates and extends the patterns observed in Study 1. Generally, our quantitative strand confirmed that creative action can be tedious and labor-intensive. However, managing the creative process was just as demanding as it was crucial. It required significant time, effort, and dynamic adjustments that responded to the project's evolving needs. Teachers who found the energy to make such an effort were more likely to succeed and perceived their projects as more creative. As our qualitative interviews further demonstrated, they tended to follow the three phases of creative self-regulation, from inspiration seeking and preparation to implementing ideas, and reflecting on the results. This speaks to the validity of the creative self-regulation model (Zielińska et al., 2023; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2021) in a real-life and educationally-relevant context.

Moreover, building on findings from Study 1—yet here in more dynamic settings—we recognized three broad regulatory orientations teachers tended to adopt in guiding their creative projects. Figure 5 summarizes these patterns as derived from the static measurement of self-regulation in Study 1 and the dynamic focus of Study 2. Most often, teachers' approach to developing educational aid resembled the draft-revise profile representing a "full package" of regulatory mechanisms: from effective yet adaptable planning, through experimenting with diverse solutions, modifying ideas, and making the project design evolve, to cultivating their own and students' pride in their accomplishment and readiness to share it with others. Such a comprehensive approach to regulating the creative process clearly paid off: teachers who followed this orientation were eventually recognized as the competition laureates, and their original tool was seen as superior in both scientific and educational aspects.

The two remaining orientations were less frequent, which is quite fortunate in the case of a dysregulated profile. The only team that presented more severe difficulties with managing the process effectively was not only ranked lower in the competition (i.e., remained at the finalist status) but also was less satisfied with the project outcomes and expressed tempered enthusiasm for sharing the tool with a broader audience. Conversely, teachers whose approach aligned with the plan-execute profile felt their process unfolded seamlessly, leading precisely to the initially

envisioned outcomes. It seems probable that, if given another opportunity, these teachers would approach the project in much the same way. While they ultimately ranked lower in the competition, they still made it to the top 10 finalist teams. Thus, we caution against considering the plan-execute orientation less effective, particularly when considering the results from Study 1. To shed light on more nuanced differences between teachers' regulatory behaviors, below, we briefly recapitulate the specific patterns observed across the project phases, highlighting the insights from our profile-based interpretations.

During the forethought phase, teachers generally invested a lot of effort in planning and organizing their and their students' work. Those following the draft-revise path attempted to compile the project's *skeleton*: a holistic and flexible framework that the team could build upon as the work continued. Students' emotional reactions to ideas and their own initiative guided such project conceptualization. At this point, teachers faced the trade-off between originality and feasibility, which sometimes led them to dismiss highly innovative but risky or unrealistic concepts in favor of more feasible ones. Indeed, previous studies suggest that when children are asked to select an idea that will transform into a tangible product, they prefer more feasible but less original ideas (van Broekhoven et al., 2022). This tendency appeared to be even more prevalent among teachers in our study, who had to consider their own and their students' capabilities when selecting ideas. This consideration involved anticipating potential obstacles, which influenced teachers' feasibility assessments and informed their decision-making. Importantly, and in line with the draft-revise profile identified in Study 1, these teachers expressed a sense of tentativeness in their vision at this stage and emphasized the need to remain flexible throughout the process.

Alternatively, some teachers aimed to create a more detailed project plan, thoroughly specifying its subsequent steps and the means to complete them smoothly. Rather than letting the ideas evolve and change as they proceeded, they strived to secure everything beforehand. In doing so, they often relied on their own expertise, combined with input from the co-teacher. This is not to say that teachers adopting the plan-execute approach were overly rigid or authoritative. Their

reflections revealed a complex balance between the desire to develop a detailed and comprehensive plan and the willingness to adjust the vision if needed. They considered various directions and simulated diverse scenarios, often prompted by students' ideas. Yet, such exploratory actions were mostly present in the planning phase, resulting in a refined plan ready to be implemented.

As the project entered the performance phase, teachers adopting the draft-revise approach intensified their self-regulatory efforts even more. Their reminiscences confirmed the importance of adjusting the approach, thus echoing the findings of Study 1. These teachers recognized that everything evolved during this stage and that they modified their work through metacognitively informed reflection. Importantly, those less eager to change their projects and adhere to the plan-execute orientation eventually ranked lower in the competition.

Interestingly, the modifications teachers made—especially those aligned with the draft-revise profile—followed a bidirectional pattern: they either added more elements to the project, thus making it more complex, or removed some components, thus making it simpler yet functional. Although the latter strategy was often applied due to budget or time constraints, it is particularly noteworthy. When asked to redesign or improve an idea or object, people tend to change it by adding elements rather than removing the existing ones (Adams et al., 2021; Fillon et al., 2022). Subtracting components is more cognitively demanding and especially difficult to recognize when under a high mental load. Therefore, the fact that the teachers could recognize the possibility of improving the project by reducing its complexity speaks for their high level of self-regulatory engagement.

After completing the projects, teachers were mostly enthusiastic about sharing their outcomes with others. This tendency was especially prominent among future laureates, demonstrating the metacognitive accuracy of their judgments. While some teachers highlighted areas that could be improved in the final product, they were all generally pleased with what had been achieved. This is not surprising, given that Study 2 involved teachers whose projects at least qualified for the competition's finals: even if they were not declared laureates, their tools were

already appreciated. However, there was one notable exception. The team fitting the dysregulated profile, marked by high initial obstacle expectations evoking negative emotions and a later reduction of the project's scope, seemed more relieved than proud upon completing their project.

The interviews further revealed that emotions, particularly pride and satisfaction, drove teachers' readiness to present their projects publicly. The hope of inspiring other teachers and providing them with useful educational tools was a crucial motivation for sharing their results. This finding is consistent with previous research that identified socially-oriented motives for engaging in creative action, such as the desire for recognition or the drive to help others and please them (Benedek et al., 2020).

Importantly, our qualitative strand sheds light on teacher-student interactions while regulating the creative process. All teachers perceived the within-team dialogues as highly inspiring and serving as guidelines across the project stages. Sometimes, these exchanges led to tempering overly high expectations, as if activating the strategy of mental contrasting (Oettingen et al., 2000), where an idealistic vision is juxtaposed against present constraints, thus promoting more realistic goal setting. More often, however, teacher-student interactions encouraged the generation of brave ideas, willingness to take adaptive risks (Beghetto et al., 2021), and supported bold attitudes toward the creative process among team members (Ivcevic & Hoffmann, 2021). Notably, the role of these co-regulative efforts in the draft-revise orientation was evident throughout all phases, while in the plan-execute-profiled teams, it was more pronounced during project preparations.

Limitations

The goal of Study 2 was to gain a better understanding of how self-regulation contributes to teachers' creative agency in a more dynamic context. Although both the small sample size and its unique character limit the generalizability of our findings, the fact that the projects analyzed were educationally oriented and carried out over a long-term period speaks to the external validity of our results. However, the teachers' high engagement and—given the finalist status—their creative

competencies might not be representative of the general teacher population. Thus, further studies are needed to verify the applicability of the present findings to other educational settings.

It is also essential to acknowledge that the projects involved collaborative efforts. While our qualitative analyses sought to disentangle the regulatory behaviors of teachers and students, more tailored designs, such as observational studies or the inclusion of both teachers and students in the quantitative and qualitative measurements, are needed to glean more insight into their co-regulative efforts (Hadwin et al., 2018; Järvelä et al., 2021). However, our in-depth interviews proved effective in demonstrating that when introducing creativity to the classroom, both teachers and students actively interact, observe mutual reactions, and adjust their approach accordingly.

General Discussion

How do teachers create? Across two studies, we approached this question by focusing on the essential ingredients of teachers' motivation and ability to function creatively: their self-beliefs (Study 1) and self-regulation (Study 1 and Study 2). We specifically situated our investigation within a school context by having teachers reflect on their most creative activity in professional practice (Study 1) or by utilizing data from a more dynamic setting where teachers, together with their students, designed and implemented an educational aid (Study 2).

Both studies—although Study 1 more directly—emphasized the importance of teachers' creative self-beliefs in achieving a creative outcome. Teachers who trusted their creative abilities and recognized the personal value of creativity undertook more original and useful initiatives. Additionally, teachers' self-beliefs fueled their self-regulatory efforts, leading to better performance both directly and indirectly by encouraging them to plan, monitor, and adjust their actions more actively. It is important to note, however, that there are also other factors that inform teachers' creative agency and make them more or less eager to operate creatively. Indeed, as our analysis demonstrated, positive self-perceptions and effective self-regulation were necessary but insufficient to succeed in teachers' creative pursuits. Other possible barriers that prevent teachers from being more creative in their practices include overloaded and inflexible curricula, limited time, resources,

and training, or high-stakes exams and their demands, as well as other factors (for a comprehensive overview of teacher-perceived barriers and enablers to introducing creativity to the classroom, see Bereczki & Kárpáti, 2018).

In general, our findings support a recently offered framework of creative self-regulation (Zielińska et al., 2023; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2021). Specifically, we demonstrated its relevance in teacher-oriented research and identified the most crucial regulatory tactics supporting teachers' creative endeavors: uncertainty acceptance while preparing for a project, adjusting the approach when engaging in goal-oriented activities, and readiness for sharing the outcomes once the work is complete. Furthermore, our results align with and extend the tenets of the Creative Behavior as an Agentic Action model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) by demonstrating the interplay between self-beliefs and self-regulation in the decision to act creatively.

Creativity in Teacher Professional Development

The discourse on creativity in the classroom centers on students' creative development and how teachers can support or hinder students' creative growth. However, researchers add to this conversation by highlighting the importance of teachers' creativity (Patston et al., 2017) and how it can translate and be fostered in educational settings (Anderson et al., 2022). Based on the present research findings, we argue that to take an active role in introducing creativity to the classroom, teachers need both strong yet adequate creative self-beliefs—confidence and centrality—and self-regulatory resources to manage creative activities effectively. Increasing teachers' creative agency via strengthening these two components can lead to positive changes, including a willingness to experiment with creative teaching methods, responsiveness to student-initiated creative openings (Beghetto, 2016b), and a positive attitude toward various forms of students' creative expressions. Therefore, cultivating creativity in schools is an invitation for creative engagement, not just for students but also for teachers.

This naturally raises the question of how to strengthen teachers' creative agency by addressing their self-beliefs and regulatory competencies. Research from the creativity field

(Karwowski, Czerwonka, Lebuda, et al., 2020; Mathisen & Bronnick, 2009; O'Connor et al., 2013; Zielińska, Lebuda, & Karwowski, 2022a) and beyond (e.g., Yeager & Walton, 2011) highlights the malleability of self-beliefs, viewing them as surface characteristics of personality (Asendorpf & Van Aken, 2003; Lebuda et al., 2021) that can be changed through socio-environmental influences, training and intervention, and deliberate personal effort. There is, however, a lack of empirically validated methods of supporting self-regulation in creativity. Studies on self-regulated learning offer promising guidance on encouraging people to use cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational strategies when working on a problem (e.g., Daumiller & Dresel, 2019; Schmitz & Wiese, 2006). Based on these resources, we propose key directions for enhancing teachers' creative agency by focusing on their self-beliefs and self-regulation.

Implications for practice

A fundamental approach to enhancing teachers' agency is providing them with creative expression opportunities. Workshops, competitions, and courses that are both accessible and give a chance to *prove oneself* can enrich teachers' creative experiences and build their creative confidence. These initiatives may be implemented independently or as part of programs designed to train high-expectation teachers (Rubie-Davies et al., 2015). Equally important, however, are teacher-initiated creative activities undertaken outside of the school context. They can have a similar confidence-boosting effect and increase teachers' willingness to bring their interests into the classroom and inspire students.

While being creative role models for their students, teachers can also learn from one another's successful creative initiatives. Two key aspects of teachers-as-models-for-teachers should be emphasized. Firstly, it is important to underline the positive feedback teachers receive from their students, parents, school authorities, and other sources of recognition, as well as self-satisfaction and pride with their creative efforts. This can inspire teachers to try out similar activities, adapt them to their practice, and tailor them to their needs.

Secondly, it might be informative to share with teachers the ups and downs experienced by their colleagues in their creative pursuits. Through such examples, teachers can learn that there is nothing wrong with struggling during the creative process and how important it is to persist and maintain efforts despite obstacles. This can strengthen teachers' ability to engage in mental contrasting, which involves juxtaposing desired goals with potential barriers and formulating ways to manage them (Duckworth et al., 2011; Oettingen et al., 2000). Also, by observing effective and ineffective strategies used by others, teachers can reflect on how these strategies would work for themselves and come up with their own tactics. In turn, this might activate more intricate regulatory orientations, prompting teachers to discover the most suitable way to navigate the creative challenges: either through intensive and detailed planning (plan-execute approach) or more flexible and adaptive adjustments (draft-revise approach).

Research has already highlighted the benefits of re-shaping teachers' understanding and beliefs about creativity, such as whether creative potential can grow (Anderson et al., 2022) or whether creativity is limited to the arts (Patston et al., 2018). Building on that, we suggest that expanding teachers' knowledge about the self-regulatory aspects of the creative process is particularly valuable. Teachers might learn how the effortful, strategic, and goal-directed approach can scaffold creative action and that the sense of difficulty and struggle can signal progress or even personal growth (Woolley & Fishbach, 2022). Challenging common misconceptions about creativity being solely spontaneous (e.g., Benedek et al., 2021) can be an inspirational starting point for further discussion on the importance of planning, setting goals, monitoring progress, and evaluating strategies used. Additionally, teachers can be encouraged to reflect on what distinguishes creative goal pursuit from other projects oriented toward a specific outcome (e.g., following a pre-defined curriculum), thus recognizing the uncertainty inherent in creative action. This might prompt a reflection on one's readiness to take intellectual risks (Beghetto et al., 2021), tolerance for ambiguity (Zenasni et al., 2008), or ability to act strategically not only while solving but also identifying problems (Rubenstein et al., 2020). Most crucially, the discussion on the controllable nature of the

creative process can build teachers' conviction that creative initiatives in the work context can be effectively managed and spur their willingness to try and refine various strategies for navigating such endeavors. As demonstrated across the two studies, no universal regulatory pattern guarantees successful creative action, and only a dysregulated approach—at least in this research—hindered performance and resulted in less satisfactory outcomes.

Yet, to enhance teachers' self-regulatory skills during real-life creative endeavors, it is crucial to provide practical exercises in addition to theoretical training. For instance, presenting teachers with brief creative tasks while prompting them to reflect on how they work, where they are in the process, and how to respond to new ideas or changing circumstances can increase their self-regulatory engagement and spur a similar approach in the future. Such training can also reduce teachers' creativity anxiety (Daker et al., 2020) and help them feel less intimidated by the demands of the creative process. Additionally, when invited to work on creative problems, teachers can be encouraged to generate multiple initial ideas and drafts, revise them, and prioritize progress and excellence over unrealistic standards. This can help overcome perfectionistic tendencies and concerns that impede creative performance (Goulet-Pelletier et al., 2022).

Finally, teachers functioning in the self-reflective phase of the creative process should be supported, with a focus on developing adaptive reactions to the final outcomes. This includes recognizing sources of satisfaction, different attributions made, and a tendency to satisfy (Tromp, 2023). Also, it is valuable for teachers to reflect on how others might react to their creative projects and what criteria could determine social evaluation (e.g., originality, usefulness in a specific context, but also individualized points of view; see Anderson et al., 2023). How teachers respond to what they achieve and the feedback they receive not only impacts their willingness to share their work with others but also affects their motivation to take on creative challenges in the future (Rubenstein, Callan, et al., 2018; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2021).

Conclusion

Creativity is a uniquely human characteristic that not only allows the greatest discoveries to be made and pieces of art to be created, but also makes our lives better and more fulfilled (Kaufman, 2018, 2023). Therefore, it is no surprise that schools and educational systems worldwide are expected to support and strengthen students' creative thought and action. At the same time, however, teachers' creative functioning and its conditions are overlooked. The two studies presented in this paper demonstrate that teachers' creative self-beliefs—their creative confidence and centrality of creativity—are vital factors that increase the likelihood of creative activity and result in more creative outcomes. Moreover, creative self-beliefs seem to shape creative self-regulation and encourage using various tactics conducive to creativity. We found that being low in creative self-beliefs makes effective self-regulation hardly possible. Even more importantly, both self-beliefs and self-regulation appear to be necessary conditions for developing creative projects: their low level precludes teachers from proposing novel and valuable solutions, or at least makes it highly unlikely. Yet, there is no singular, universally applicable approach for achieving creative and educationally-relevant outcomes. Notably, interactions with students often inspire teachers to reconsider and adjust their regulatory orientations. Overall, this investigation provides an argument that becoming a creative agent requires a sense of efficacy and seeing the importance of creativity, as well as using various tactics and strategies when planning, conducting, and evaluating the results of an activity.

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